

Analysis of Prevalence and Outcomes of Single Coronary Artery Detected on Coronary Computed Tomography Angiography (CCTA)

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Abstract

Introduction: Coronary artery disease (CAD) is one of the leading causes of mortality and morbidity in Singapore.

Objectives: Therefore, the main objective of this study is to analyse the prevalence and outcomes of single coronary artery detected on coronary computed tomography angiography (CCTA).

Material and methods: This descriptive study was conducted in Jinnah Hospital Lahore during April 2020 till November 2020. The data was collected from 100 patients. Prior to the scan, electrocardiogram (ECG), heart rate, and blood pressure of all patients were checked. Procedure preparation included administration of 25–100 mg of atenolol orally to all patients with a baseline heart rate >70 beats/min to lower the heart rate. All scans started with topogram, followed by a prospective ECG-gated nonenhanced CT scan at 75% of RR interval.

Results: In SCA group, values of SBP, DBP, PP and BMI were higher than the control group, and the difference had statistical significance ($P < 0.05$). There was no significant difference between the two groups in age, FBG, TG, TC, HDL-C and LDL-C. Other SCA included RII-C, RII-A, and RII-S, two in each class. One patient had RI and one had LII-P. Two patients had coronary artery bypass graft.

Conclusion: It is concluded that SCA is divided into different subtypes based on the course of the anomalous artery. Awareness of these types is essential as it has an implication for planning patient management.

Keywords

CAD, CCTA, ECG, SCA

1. Introduction

Coronary artery disease (CAD) is one of the leading causes of mortality and morbidity in Singapore. Catheter coronary angiography (CCA) is considered the gold standard for diagnosing CAD, as it is highly reliable and has the ability to determine

the extent, location and severity of coronary obstructive lesions [1]. However, CCA is not suitable for all patients with suspected CAD due to its invasive nature and risk of complications. Furthermore, not all conventional angiography procedures proceed to intervention. Weighing the risks of CCA for a patient who may not require intervention may tip the scales in favour of a noninvasive test for diagnosing coronary stenosis [2].

Single coronary artery (SCA) is a congenital anomaly that is usually discovered incidentally and has an estimated incidence ranging between 0.024% and 0.066% among patients undergoing routine coronary artery catheterization [3]. SCA can be either an isolated anomaly or associated with other congenital abnormalities such as coronary artery fistula and bicuspid aortic valve [4]. Based on the site of origin and anatomical distribution of the branches, Lipton et al. classified SCA into two main categories: "R," right type, and "L," left type. These two types were further divided into I, II, and III subtypes according to the anatomical courses of the branches [5].

A single coronary artery (SCA) is defined as a single aortic orifice or origin providing for all of the coronary blood perfusion of the entire myocardium. An equal distribution is found between SCA originating from the right sinus of Valsalva (RSV) and the LSV [6]. Exact delineation of the course of the abnormal coronaries relative to the aorta and pulmonary artery is of major importance as myocardial ischemia during exertion can be caused by kinking or squeezing of the branches of the anomalous SCA between the aorta and pulmonary artery. CAG is the first diagnostic tool in the detection of a SCA. Once abnormal coronary arteries are suspected, multi-slice computed tomography (MSCT) and cardiac magnetic resonance (CMR) imaging scans are excellent tools for non-invasive determination of the course of the abnormal coronaries relative to the aorta and pulmonary artery [7].

Therefore, the main objective of this study is to analyse the prevalence and outcomes of single coronary artery detected on coronary computed tomography angiography (CCTA).

2. Material and methods

This descriptive study was conducted in Jinnah Hospital Lahore during April 2020 till November 2020. The data was collected from 100 patients. Prior to the scan, electrocardiogram (ECG), heart rate, and blood pressure of all patients were checked. Procedure preparation included administration of 25–100 mg of atenolol orally to all patients with a baseline heart rate >70 beats/min to lower the heart rate. All scans started with topogram, followed by a prospective ECG-gated nonenhanced CT scan at 75% of RR interval. The CCTA scan was performed by injecting 60 to 75 mL of contrast followed by 30 mL of saline solution at a rate of 6 mL/s. In the contrast-enhanced scan, ECG-gated prospective or retrospective scan with a slice thickness of 0.6 mm was acquired during breath holding in inspiration. The scan parameters were adjusted automatically or manually to acquire the best quality with the least radiation dose.

2.1. Statistical Analysis

Data was presented by average value $\pm$ standard deviation. Comparison between groups was evaluated first by normality and homogeneity test for variance. Those passed the test would be evaluated by t-test. $P < 0.05$ was regarded significant of the differences in statistics.

3. Results

1. SCA Group and Control Group in General Materials

In SCA group, values of SBP, DBP, PP and BMI were higher than the control group, and the difference had statistical significance ($P < 0.05$). There was no significant difference between the two groups in age, FBG, TG, TC, HDL-C and LDL-C ($P < 0.05$)(Table 1).

	SCA Group(n=50)	Control Group (n=50)	t Value	p Value
Age (Year)	56.56 $\pm$ 8.46	53.64 $\pm$ 8.36	1.716	0.081
BMI (kg/m ²)	24.31 $\pm$ 2.26	23.37 $\pm$ 2.09	2.195	0.031
SBP (mmHg)	140.36 $\pm$ 15.70	116.53 $\pm$ 13.46	8.248	0.000
DBP (mmHg)	87.94 $\pm$ 10.69	75.81 $\pm$ 9.94	5.967	0.000
PP (mmHg)	52.42 $\pm$ 12.87	40.72 $\pm$ 8.74	5.426	0.000
FBG (mmol/L)	5.12 $\pm$ 0.65	5.06 $\pm$ 0.49	1.764	0.081
TG (mmol/L)	1.74 $\pm$ 0.75	1.69 $\pm$ 0.86	1.838	0.071
TC (mmol/L)	4.95 $\pm$ 0.76	4.88 $\pm$ 0.82	1.712	0.090
HDL-C (mmol/L)	1.30 $\pm$ 0.43	1.31 $\pm$ 0.56	1.717	0.089
LDL-C (mmol/L)	3.46 $\pm$ 0.58	3.38 $\pm$ 0.66	1.139	0.266

Note : BMI : body mass index ; SBP : systolic blood pressure ; DBP : diastolic blood pressure ; PP : pulse pressure ; FBG : fasting blood glucose ; TG : triglyceride ; TC : total cholesterol ; HDL-C : high-density lipoprotein ; LDL-C: low-density lipoprotein

2. Comparison between two groups in structural and functional parameters of coronary artery

IMT, α , β , and PWV of bilateral carotid artery in SCA group were higher than those in control group; CC was lower than that in control group. Those differences were significant in statistics ($p < 0.05$)(Table 2, Table 3).

Group	IMT(μ m)	CC (mm ² /KPa)	α	β	PWV(m/s)
SCA Group	694.88 $\pm$ 77.63	0.89 $\pm$ 0.13	5.68 $\pm$ 1.23	11.25 $\pm$ 1.01	9.49 $\pm$ 1.09
Control Group	586.87 $\pm$ 62.12	0.96 $\pm$ 0.08	4.77 $\pm$ 0.62	9.24 $\pm$ 1.24	7.22 $\pm$ 1.11
T value	7.818	-3.115	4.712	9.004	10.482

<i>P</i> value	0.000	0.002	0.000	0.000	0.000
Note : IMT : intima-media thickness ; CC : compliance coefficient ; α : stiffness indicator ; β : stiffness parameter PWV : pulse wave velocity					

Table 3: Comparison between SCA Group and Control Group in structural and functional parameters of the right arteriacarotiscommunis ($\bar{x} \pm s$)($\bar{x} \pm s$)

Group	IMT(μm)	CC (mm^2/KPa)	α	β	PWV(m/s)
SCA Group	637.42 $\pm$ 93.30	0.91 $\pm$ 0.09	5.46 $\pm$ 1.19	11.14 $\pm$ 1.02	9.29 $\pm$ 1.05
Control Group	545.13 $\pm$ 62.28	0.99 $\pm$ 0.08	4.74 $\pm$ 0.96	9.13 $\pm$ 1.20	7.07 $\pm$ 1.22
<i>t</i> value	5.869	-4.899	3.339	9.094	9.865
<i>p</i> value	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000

3. Assessment of Structure and Elastic Parameters of coronary artery to SCA Scanning Accuracy

Set the results of head MRI as the golden standard, IMT, α , β , CC and PWV as variables. Did ROC cure analysis regarding SCA as a state variable to assess the accuracy of SCA scanning test. Considering that there were differences in systolic pressure, diastolic pressure and pulse pressure between two groups and that blood pressure had some effect on the accuracy of SCA scanning diagnosis, applied overfitting PP hierarchical model to get an ROC curve when $PP \leq 45\text{mmHg}$ and $PP > 45\text{mmHg}$. The results showed that the accuracy of IMT, β and PWV measuring SCA was higher when $PP \leq 45\text{mmHg}$, and the area below the curve was $PWV > \beta > IMT$. The accuracy of IMT, α , β and PWV measuring SCA was higher when $PP > 45\text{mmHg}$, and the area below the curve was $PWV > \beta > \alpha > IMT$.

Table 4 Comparison of structural and elastic parameters of coronary artery to SCA diagnostic value when $PP \leq 45\text{mmHg}$

Parameters	AUC	<i>P</i> value	Standard Error	AUC 95%CI	
				Lower limit	Upper limit
LIMT (μm)	0.833	0.000	0.064	0.707	0.960
RIMT (μm)	0.728	0.006	0.081	0.569	0.888
LCC (mm^2/kPa)	0.474	0.757	0.103	0.273	0.676
RCC (mm^2/kPa)	0.296	0.015	0.076	0.147	0.446
L α	0.606	0.203	0.080	0.450	0.763
R α	0.562	0.461	0.086	0.394	0.730
L β	0.878	0.000	0.052	0.776	0.980
R β	0.887	0.000	0.057	0.774	0.999
LPWV (m/s)	0.904	0.000	0.042	0.821	0.987
RPWV (m/s)	0.912	0.000	0.044	0.826	0.998

Note: IMT, β and PWV have high diagnostic value to SCA, and there is no error when diagnosing SCA. α and CC have low diagnostic value to SCA. AUC: area under the curve; AUC 95% CI: area under the curve 95% credibility interval.

Figure 1 PP $\leq$ 45mmHg, ROC curve of SCA examined by IMT. Blue line stands for left IMT, green line stands for right IMT.

Figure 2 PP $\leq$ 45mmHg, ROC curve of SCA examined by β . Blue line stands for left β , green line stands for right β .

Figure 3 PP $\leq$ 45mmHg, ROC curve of SCA examined by PWV. Blue line stands for left PWV, green line stands for right PWV.

Figure 6. PP > 45mmHg, ROC curve of SCA examined by β . Blue line stands for left β , green line stands for right β .

Figure 7. PP > 45mmHg ROC curve of SCA examined by PWV. Blue line stands for left PWV, green line stands for right PWV.

Resting electrocardiograph. A: Electrocardiograph during chest pain depicting transmural ischemia in the infero-posterior leads; B: Followed by a non-sustained

monomorphic ventricular tachycardia; C: Coronary angiography showed absence of the right coronary ostium and a single coronary artery arising from the left sinus of Valsalva with normal origin of the left coronary artery (LCA) having normal anatomical course of the left main stem, the left anterior descending, and the circumflex artery (Lipton L-I); D: The LCA supplies the entire myocardial tissue. No significant stenoses were found. The right coronary artery (RCA) appeared as a continuation of the distal left circumflex artery to the right atrioventricular groove and terminated near the RSV (Lipton L-I). LAD: Left anterior descending; LMCA: Left main coronary artery; RCX: Ramus circumflexus; RDP: Ramus descending posterior; OM: Obtuse marginal.

4. Discussion

SCA is a series of diseases which affects encephalic small vessels, manifested as loss of smooth muscle cells in vascular walls, deposition of fibrous transparent materials, thickness of vascular walls and stenosis of lumen. SCA is one of the reasons of ischemic stroke [8]. At present, the pathogenesis for SCA is still unclear. It is assumed that SCA is induced by the combined actions of various cerebrovascular disease risks and genetic factors and then give rise to all kinds of clinical symptoms [9]. SCA can be diagnosed by different diagnostic modalities including conventional coronary angiography, coronary computed tomography angiography, and cardiac MRI [10-12]. Conventional coronary angiography is the gold standard for assessment of the coronary artery; however, it is an invasive procedure and has a risk of complications [13]. Moreover, even with multiple projections and angiographic views, delineation of the anatomy of the complex cases can be difficult [14-16]. On the contrary, coronary computed tomography angiography (CCTA) is a noninvasive diagnostic tool with high temporal and spatial resolution that has emerged as a gold standard for detection and characterization of coronary artery anomalies [17-19]. CCTA can precisely delineate the course of the anomalous artery and provide 3-dimensional information about the relation of the anomalous artery to other cardiovascular structures, namely, cardiac chambers and major arteries [20]. However, despite the advances in CT technology to reduce radiation exposure, CCTA is still an ionizing examination. Cardiovascular MRI, on the contrary, is a nonionizing test that can be used to detect SCA and delineate the anatomy of the anomalous coronary artery along with the viability assessment of the myocardium; however, it has a lower temporal and spatial resolution compared to the CCTA. Moreover, MRI is less available than other diagnostic modalities and contraindicated in patients with pacemakers [21]. All our patients with SCA were diagnosed by CCTA, by which we were able to precisely delineate the origin and the course of the anomalous artery.

The presence of atherosclerotic disease in patients with coronary artery anomaly has a clinical implication, particularly when the decision is to be made between percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) and coronary artery bypass graft (CABG) [23]. Moreover, awareness of presence of coronary artery anomalies and their anomalous course prior to CABG is crucial to avoid potential surgical complications

as unrecognized anomalous artery can be excluded from perfusion during cardiopulmonary bypass or might be unintentionally damaged.

5. Conclusion

It is concluded that SCA is divided into different subtypes based on the course of the anomalous artery. Awareness of these types is essential as it has an implication for planning patient management. Coronary computed tomography angiography has an important role in diagnosis of different classes of SCA.

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